

CULTIVATING EMOTIONAL AND SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE IN AN AI DRIVEN WORLD THROUGH YOGA: A REVIEW

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Abstract

Development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and digitalization have brought significant changes in all walks of life. This rapid revolution of artificial intelligence (AI) is shaping and reshaping our lives, work, and social interactions. AI has become embedded in our routines and its impact on ethics and spirituality gained noticeable significance. Ethical dimension has emerged as guiding principle, while spirituality concerns to our connection to higher realms and life's meaning. It brought benefits as well as ethical apprehensions like privacy, transparency, and accountability. Thus, it is necessary to examine and maintain mindfulness, ethics, and spirituality in the era of AI which is challenging our habits. According to Aristotle, 'it is our choice of good or evil determines our character and not our opinion about good or bad,' so it is necessary to know oneself to be an excellent being by disciplining the habit. Now question arises can AI help us to grow an individual with the quality of emotional and spiritual intelligence. Yoga being an integral part of life has a substantial and positive impact on emotional and spiritual intelligence. This research paper tries to explore AI's intersection and interrelation with ethics and spirituality, enquiring into its ethical and spiritual implications on individual. In the midst of rapid technological advancement, maintaining mindfulness and ethical conduct is crucial because we easily become prey to this quick fix technology. Spiritual growth is a conscious involvement in a conscious awareness of matter, life, body, mind, soul and spirit. Spiritual intelligence is more than individual mental ability. It helps to connect the personal to the transpersonal and the self to spirit; thus, the real aim of yoga is establishing union of finite self with infinite self.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Digital Technology, Yogic Sadhana, Spiritual Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, Pratipaksha Bhavana, Chitta Bhumi, Chitta Vritti, Vasudaiva Kutumbakam.

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1. Introduction

Development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and digitalization have brought significant changes in all walks of life. This rapid revolution of artificial intelligence (AI) is shaping and reshaping our lives, work, and social interactions. AI has become embedded in our routines and its impact on ethics and spirituality gained noticeable significance. Ethical dimension has emerged as guiding principle, while spirituality concerns to our connection to higher realms and life's meaning. AI shapes society significantly and impact ethics and spirituality. It brought benefits as well as ethical apprehensions like privacy, transparency, and accountability. This research article tries to explore

AI's intersection and interrelation with ethics and spirituality, enquiring into its ethical implications and spiritual effects on individual. In the midst of rapid technological advancement, maintaining mindfulness and ethical conduct is crucial because we easily become pray of this quick fix technology. Therefore, it is necessary to examines and maintain mindfulness, ethics, and spirituality in the era of AI which is challenging our habits. According to Aristotle, 'it is our choice of good or evil determines our character and not our opinion about good or bad,'¹ so it is necessary to know oneself to be an excellent being.

Artificial intelligence has captured the world's attention in recent times. This remarkable tool has simplified our lives and provided abundance knowledge and information. It is imperative that we understand artificial intelligence, embrace it as a powerful assistant, and cultivate a mutually beneficial partnership with it. We know that social media technology influences human interaction and self-esteem. This technology inclines to reduce us to users and products, due to constant usage of this technology people are dehumanized and human dignity is at toss. This technology is connecting us and also manipulating, polarizing, controlling, monetizing, and distracting us. Constantly and freely, we share personal data with personal choice without thinking how it will use it. Thus, we can say AI can easily add spices to this toxic cocktail.

Artificial Intelligence is a machine with human-level intelligence is still a science fiction. AI cannot reproduce qualities that make us human, like creativity, natural intelligence, telepathy, empathy and spiritual connection. It is difficult for AI to understand spiritual concepts like mindfulness, gratitude or the meaning and purpose of life unless algorithm is made. Thus, AI continues altering our lives and enhancing human capabilities but human intelligence is complicated. Wisdom, judgment, emotion, creativity, and ingenuity are hard to reduce to algorithms and code. For the predictable future, humans and machines will collaborate, not compete with each other. AI can complement human intelligence, not replace or duplicate it. Spiritual and emotional intelligence connects us to greater than ourselves and makes us human and not machine. It will be difficult for technology to replace it. Spiritual and emotional intelligence connect us to something greater, nurtures human qualities like contentment and divinity, and provides life with profound and meaning shape who we are which AI cannot do it; spiritual intelligence remains uniquely human.

AI has transformed how we should work and make choices, but it also poses ethical and societal threats including algorithmic discrimination and dehumanization. It is critical to take into account corporate culture, emotional intelligence, cooperation, communication, and constant learning while using AI systems in the workplace. It has been demonstrated that emotional intelligence surges AI adoption, efficacy, and performance across a variety of sectors. But ethical concerns and trouble making decisions are also rising. Usage of AI to be truly beneficial to society, if is designed with the values of empathy, compassion, and respect for human dignity. Mindfulness and ethical decision will help us to cultivate these moral values and integrate them into our technological creations. To nurture these values and virtues among individual, we need to take help of our ancient heritage i.e. philosophy of yoga.

Effective collaboration, communication, and corporate culture are crucial for successful AI adoption, and continuing learning and development are essential for enhancing decision-making abilities in today competitive world. AI ethics in the workplace necessitate a comprehensive strategy that considers both technical and non-technical aspects. AI is expanding at an

¹ Aristotle, '*Aristotle the Niccomachean Ethics*', p.58, Wordsworth Edition Ltd., 1996, Great Britain.

unprecedented pace, transforming the world of work in ways we never thought possible. From automating mundane tasks to improve decision-making processes, AI reshapes organizational structures and creates new growth opportunities. While AI may be able to perform complex tasks, but it lacks one important attribute that is essential for human interactions i.e. emotional and spiritual intelligence (EQ and SQ). The question arises; does EQ matter in the new world of AI? The answer is a resounding yes, not only for individuals but also for businesses, especially in the age of AI. Organizations face constant changes and challenges, and disruptive innovations such as AI make the future uncertain. Leaders with high levels of EQ are more resilient and adaptive and can manage change effectively. They can inspire and motivate their teams and handle the ambiguity and complexity of change.

In a world where virtual communication is must, the ability to connect with others on an emotional level is necessity. EQ and SQ is essential in building strong relationships, creating trust and loyalty, resolving conflicts, and managing diverse perspectives effectively. Unlike AI, humans can sense emotions and pick up nonverbal cues, which is vital for improving collaboration and communication. Innovation and creativity are crucial for businesses to stay ahead in this ever-changing world. People with high EQ and SQ have a greater ability to think out of the box, generate new ideas, and solve complex problems. They can also empathize with customers, identify unachieved needs, and develop solutions that exceed expectations. Leaders with high EQ can create a positive work culture that fosters creativity, respect, and appreciation. They can also connect with employees personally, understand their problems and motivations, and create an environment that nurtures their talents and skills. As AI expands, ethical issues such as privacy breaches, algorithmic biases, and job displacement are becoming more significant concerns. Thus, EQ and SQ is crucial in addressing these issues by balancing technological advancements with social responsibility. Leaders with high EQ and SQ can exercise empathy, consider different perspectives, and prioritize the long-term benefits for all stakeholders. They can also communicate the importance of ethical practices to their teams and ensure the ethical use of AI. AI can help us perform complex tasks, but to connect with others emotionally, a key element for effective leadership and collaboration is available uniquely in humans. Business leaders, HR professionals, coaches, and consultants must realize the significance of EQ and SQ in the age of AI and cultivate their EQ and SQ to prepare themselves and their organizations better for the future growth and achievements.

With Artificial intelligence impeccably assuming the functions traditionally attributed to the left brain, humans can now connect their full potential by focusing on the expansion of their right brain capabilities. This requires sharpening the critical analytical skills, fostering compassion, empathy, inclusiveness and more. As AI takes the load of our IQ related work, can we turn our attention towards nurturing and enhancing our emotional and spiritual intelligence. AI caters to our intellectual curiosity, but emotional and spiritual intelligence kindles our thirst for wisdom and deeper understanding, fostering personal growth and transformation by taking everyone together and accepting the others otherness.

Artificial intelligence has indisputably revolutionised our world. The word artificial signifies a lack of naturalness or spontaneity, which is the exclusive realm of the spirit. However, the dormant power of emotional and spiritual intelligence within us holds the promise of a deeper and more fulfilling existence. By embracing and connecting this inner wellspring of wisdom, we can complement and supplement wonders of technology, creating a more holistic and enriching life. As we venture into the future, let us remember that true fulfilment lies not only in the capabilities of AI but also in the nurturing and expansion of our own consciousness which is our essence. We

need to develop AI which will be human-centric, or else we will be facing a dystopic future. Human-centric means centred in humanistic values which embrace human dignity and rights and will nurture web of human relationality into relation to creation, fellow-humans, our own self and God or Ultimate Reality which is not immanent but transcendent.

2. Development of Emotional and Spiritual Intelligence through Yoga

Yoga philosophy can come to our rescue being an ancient science and art based on harmonizing system which brings equilibrium of mind, body and spirit. This tradition is 5000 years old. This is a comprehensive system for wellbeing at all levels; physical, mental, emotional and spiritual. Yoga helps to improve the quality of life in diversified manner such as fitness, stress relief, wellness, vitality, mental clarity healing, peace of mind and spiritual growth. The word 'Yoga' is derived from Sanskrit root word 'Yuj' means 'union', 'yoke or join' 'Yujyate anena iti yogah'². Thus, yoga is union of finite self with infinite self.

Patanjali's Yoga Sutras is an ancient text on the practice of yoga. The text is divided into four chapters or books or pada and serves as a comprehensive guide to the practice of yoga and spiritual development. The second chapter of the text known as the Sadhana Pada, contains the famous verse, 'Yogastha Chitta Vritti Nirodha' (P.S.Y.1.2)³ which has become cornerstone of yoga philosophy and a key principle for improving awareness and spiritual intelligence in the era of AI driven world. This phrase is translated as 'yoga is the cessation of the fluctuations of the mind'; it means yoga can bring compulsive thinking under control. This sutra constantly reminds us that one can acquire the tools to be in control of one's actions and reactions and make decisions that are well thought out as opposed to being at the mercy of one's emotions and reactions. Chitta is disproportionate combination of three *gunas*; *sattva*, *rajasa*, and *tamas*. yoga is journey from outer world to inner self. The *chitta vritti* or mental modifications or fluctuations are five in number right knowledge (*pramana*), wrong knowledge (*viparya*), imagination (*vikalpa*), sleep (*nidra*), memory (*smriti*). The *vritti*'s or fluctuation can be classified as painful (*klishhta*) and non-painful (*aklishhta*), these waves of thought or *vritti*'s always affect one's ability to find truth and prevent individual to find out true self especially where we are over whelmed by technology. Understanding the five states of mind (*chitta bhumi*) i.e. *mudha*, *kshipta*, *vikshipta*, *ekagra* and *niruddha* help us to overcome the problems related to mental states and find the solutions to these problems by developing emotional and spiritual intelligence and achieve greater self-awareness and inner bliss. Therefore, yoga prepares our mind to the stormy ocean of competitive world which is agitated by sensation, perception, emotion, feelings, values etc. But yogic discipline teaches to identify ourselves with state of mind. We become what our mind is sensing, feeling, imaging at any moment. To overcome this mental modification, one need to rest in the state of oneness and this possible only through training mind with the help of yogic sadhana by inculcating the principles of *ashtanga* yoga; *yama* and *niyama*. This will influence our cognition and prepare us to behave in a particular way because they are guiding principles of conduct. Attitudes can be both positive and negative which influences our behaviour. Positive attitude prepares an individual to behave in a positive way; negative attitude brings negative proneness in one's behaviour. Simply our behaviour is the reflection of our attitudes.

²Bhide Nivedita Raghunath, 'Yoga: The way of Life Based on the Vision of Oneness', Vivekananda Kendra Prakashan Trust, Chennai 600005.

³Iyengar B.K.S., 'Light on the Yoga Sutra of Patanjali', Published by Thorsons, London, 1996, ISBN: 13-978-0-00-714516-4.

Yoga being a science of man-making deals with achieving equanimity, composure and ease at all time. It helps to control and coordinate the subtle forces in body. Yogic discipline helps us to remove one's defects and weaknesses and help to attain state of perfection, freedom and super consciousness blessedness. This state is the state of union between finite with infinite. The different types of yoga, *Hatha yoga* (physical posture), *Karma yoga* (acts of service), *Bhakti yoga* (devotion), and *Jnana yoga* (contemplation). They have one thing in common which qualifies them as forms of yoga are that they are all means of uniting body, mind, and spirit. Yoga being an integral part of the way of life has a substantial and positive impact on emotional and spiritual intelligence. Yoga contributes not only on mental health, but also on spiritual growth. Emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others, is a critical skill for achieving success and fulfilment in both personal and professional life. The components of emotional intelligence are self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivation, and social skills which form the foundation of our ability to connect with and relate to others. Beyond these five components lies a deeper wisdom that allows us to access the consciousness of the soul through spiritual intelligence. Along with inner awareness and mental growth spiritual intelligence involves the development of strong values and ethical principles.

Spiritual intelligence means as a conscious involvement in a conscious awareness of matter, life, body, mind, soul and spirit. Spiritual intelligence is more than individual mental ability. It connects the personal to the transpersonal and the self to spirit; thus, the real aim of yoga is establishing union of finite self with infinite self. Spiritual intelligence goes beyond conventional psychological development. Yoga and spiritual intelligence have theoretical and conceptual harmony with each other. Yoga influenced internal thoughts which develop the spiritual intelligence among individuals. Yoga brings a person closer to his spiritual aspect and improves the self-awareness of the individual through mental control. Intelligent quotient and emotional quotient are both important facets of human intelligence transcend both. Intelligent quotient is primarily a function of the brain and emotional intelligence, which is connected to the heart, and spiritual intelligence is an innate quality of the soul that needs to be awakened and once it is awakened it is the master of all intelligence faculties which artificial intelligence lacks, flowing from our core. Thus, spiritual intelligence is free from the ego and the 'I' sense rather it is true identity of the self, constructed in accordance with values one arrives at through reflection.

By aligning our actions with our values and not being the puppets in the hands of digital technology, we can create a sense of purpose and direction in our lives, which can navigate the complex and ambiguous world around us. It helps us to build trust and credibility with others, as we demonstrate our commitment to living a meaningful and authentic life. An individual who possesses emotional and spiritual intelligence do not search for happiness in the external competitive material world but those who are equipped with AI technology they have become slave of it. They are dependent on it for each and every assistant. But people with emotional and spiritual intelligence recognize that the mind is restricted in its ability to create genuine happiness due to illusory time bound enjoyment because it is influenced by past experiences and deeply rooted in beliefs of materialistic attachments. But an individual who is sound with emotional and spiritual intelligence segregates reality and illusory virtual world. They are capable of distinguishing between their needs and desires or wants, based on the understanding that their needs are minimal while their wants are infinite, a person with high spiritual quotient is aware that happiness is a state of mind that can only be achieved by freeing the mind from attachment. They understand that it is the soul which has the capacity to generate a permanent state of bliss. Yoga brings this awareness and helps to control the mind through various yogic postures and meditation.

Ashtanga Yoga such as *yama*, *niyama*, *asanas*, *pranayama*, *pratyahara* and meditation helps to calm down both mind and body and reduce stress and anxiety. This calming effect gives us the space to pause and reflect before responding to situations which is much needed at every juncture.

2.1 Yoga and Personality Development

To build an all-round personality into the era of digital world which encompasses physical, mental, emotional and intellectual with a spiritual basis it is necessary to adopt Yogism. Yogism is simple living in harmony with nature and concern. Simplicity, service and spirituality are the three pillars of yogism. Yoga is eternal and universal science of living. Yogism harmonises the body, mind and spirit and connects to the oneness of universe. To bring this harmony, yoga speaks about *Asthanga Marga* (Eight-fold paths). Yoga is an art, it is not the art form like any other art form but it goes beyond and touches inner self therefore yoga is the journey of the self, through the self to the self (*Bhagvad Gita* 6.20) ⁴ It is a spiritual art because it aims at total integration, unification and harmony of mind, body and self. This form of art is totalling comprehensive and inclusive. Yogic sadhana entails the coordination of the body, nervous system and mind. Regular practice of yoga helps in the enrichment of psychological as well as physiological well-being. Emotions are multifaceted states of mind and body, consisting of physiological, behavioural, and mental wellbeing to situations that needs to be balanced. An emotionally intelligent person is more positive in various aspect of life may be favourable or unfavourable situation.

Self-regulation is an individual's ability to understand one's own emotions and the to identify it. Self-motivation is the ability to direct one's emotions to recognize opportunities, achieve goals and to be more productive and active. Empathy is the skill to understand the feelings of others and act accordingly. This helps to develop social awareness which is the ability to manage various relationships, building networks and affinity for betterment of all in every walk of life. Love and compassion are a central component of spiritual intelligence, as it helps us to cultivate qualities like empathy, compassion, self-awareness, intuition and sense of interconnectedness with all things. *Bhagvad Gita* teaches that love is the highest form of devotion and it can help us to transcend our ego and connect with the divine. In Christianity, love is seen as a central tenant of the faith, with Jesus teaching that the greatest commandment is to love God and love your neighbour as yourself. Yoga and Buddhism emphasises that cultivating compassion and loving kindness towards all being is a way of transcending the illusion of separateness and achieving enlightenment. We can make a positive difference in the lives of others and contribute to a more compassionate and loving world, where AI lacks this ability of connecting people with love and affectionate.

A person who high in spiritual intelligence will demonstrate ethical behaviour including honesty, fairness and respect for others because they have mastered the art of living in a materialistic world yet remain non-attached to people and situations. They deal with and handle what is in their control and avoid resisting what is not. They are unaffected, fearless, positive, peaceful and purposeful in all situations. The quote from the Tao Te Ching reflects why cultivation of spiritual intelligence important in day today life, 'If you are depressed, you are living in the past. If you are anxious,

⁴ Swami Ranganathananda, '*Universal Message of Bhagvad Gita An Exposition of the Gitain the light of morden thought and modern needs*', Advait Ashram publication house of Ramkrishna Math, July 2000, Kolkata- 700014. ISBN: 978-81-7505-236-9

you are living in the future and if you are at peace, you are living in the present.’⁵ With the help of meditation, *pratipaksha bhavana*⁶ and other yogic sadhana one can calm down the mind by cleaning and sanitizing and bring attention back to the present moment.

The regular practice of yoga as a ‘way of life’ lays emphasis on ‘Right Thought’, ‘Right Action’, ‘Right Reaction’ and ‘Right Attitude’. The first five steps of eight-fold path (*Astanga Yoga*) are called as external or *Bahiranga Sadhana* because they aim to help the individual to gain control of one’s own attitude, senses breathing and emotions. The last three are called internal steps (*Antaranga Sadhana*) because they assist individual to take care of all mental modification. Yoga promotes self-regulation through the practice of *pranayama* (breathing techniques) and mindfulness meditation. By consciously controlling the breath and observing thoughts and emotions without judgment, practitioners can develop greater emotional stability and resilience. Through the integration of physical postures, breathing techniques, and mindfulness meditation, yoga provides a holistic approach to developing emotional and spiritual intelligence. Regular practice of yogic discipline leads to develop emotional awareness, improved stress management, greater compassion, and more fulfilling relationship with oneself and others. Breathing techniques (*pranayama*) play a crucial role in promoting emotional balance and enhancing emotional intelligence. By consciously controlling the breath, individuals can regulate their emotional responses, reduce stress and anxiety, and cultivate a greater sense of inner calm and clarity.

The practice of yoga helps to cultivate or develop spiritual intelligence by combining personal dimensions of intelligence (Intelligent quotient and emotional quotient) with a transpersonal dimension of intelligence (spiritual quotient) through yogic sadhana. Philosophical vision of the whole existence or the Indian world view is *Ekatma Jeevan Darshan* i.e. existence is interconnected, interrelated and interdependent. It is the manifestation of one’s consciousness. Thus, in today’s competitive world it is important to maintain the mental balance at various field. If a person has very high intelligent quotient it no longer means that he would be very good at management. A person also needs to have high emotional quotient to manage oneself. A person’s emotional stability would decide how one manages challenging situations. If a person has only intelligent quotient and no emotional quotient and spiritual quotient that person could be a problem to himself and others.

3. Can AI Cultivate Balance State of Mind?

‘*Samatvam Yoga Uchayate*’ (equanimity of mind) (B.G. II. 48)⁷ and ‘*Yogah Karmasu Kaushalam*’ (efficiency in action) (B.G. II.50)⁸, these two definitions from the *Bhagvad Gita* together define completely the dynamics of how the actions of a person should be and it underlines the importance of yoga in everyone’s life at every walk of life. Whatever we do, the fruits of our actions come to us. These would be either less or more than our expectations or against our expectations. Whatever may be the fruits of action we must not lose equanimity of mind. Right choice in action is yoga.

⁵ Kolambkar Ganesh, ‘*Quantum Key: Unlocking Spiritual Intelligence*’, Notion press.com, 2023, eISBN:979-8-89133-737-4

⁶ Cultivate positive thought for every negative thought. Iyengar B.K.S., ‘*Light on the Yoga Sutra of Patanjali*’, Published by Thorsons, London, 1996, ISBN: 13-978-0-00-714516-4.

⁷ Swami Ranganathananda, ‘*Universal Message of Bhagvad Gita An Exposition of the Gitain the light of morden thought and modern needs*’, Advait Ashram publication house of Ramkrishna Math, July 2000, Kolkata- 700014. ISBN: 978-81-7505-236-9

⁸ Ibid

Yoga implies exercising the right choice in action is yoga because yoga is the way quietens the mind that has become outward focused due to individualism, consumerism and materialism. We all know that highly agitated mind is the cause of all human sufferings. The comfort level of man has gone up, but he is more dissatisfied, as he identifies himself with materialistic technological world and try to possess unnecessarily more and more than one's need, which leads to unhappiness. Patañjali in one of the *Yoga Sūtra* emphasizes the positive attitudes of friendliness, compassion, gladness and indifference respectively towards happy, sad (suffering), virtuous and vicious people and events. Yogic attitudes protect a person from unwanted negativity and help in proper development of emotional, social and spiritual dimensions of his or her personality.

'Maitrī-karunā-muditopekṣāṇāmsukha-duḥkha-puṇy-āpuṇyaviṣayāṇāmbhāvanātaścitta-prasādanam.' (P.Y.S. 1.33.)⁹ It means 'in relation to happiness, misery, virtue and vice, by cultivating the attitude of friendliness, compassion, gladness and indifference respectively, the mind becomes purified and peaceful'. Developing

With the help of mindfulness meditation one can develop greater control over one's reactions and emotions, making it easier to handle stress and conflicts. By integrating yoga in daily life one can face life challenges and problems with a greater sense of ease and confidence with balance approach. The ability to regulate emotions is crucial part of emotional intelligence. When one practices self-regulation or self-discipline they can respond to the challenging situations with greater thoughtfulness and ease. We do not allow our emotional impulses to dictate us rather we become more proficient at handling our feelings in a balanced manner in This approach helps us to manage conflicts more efficiently, make better decisions and maintain healthier relationships, which are the important components of emotional intelligence. Question is: Can AI handle conflicting situations in empathetic and affectionate way? But Yoga teaches us to kinder and more compassionate towards oneself and others. It helps to develop true sense of compassion and empathy; where one learns how to interact and understand others by developing self-compassion and understand and respect otherness of others. This fosters our sense of unity and support, which strengthens our ability to connect with people on a deeper level and to navigate life challenges with greater resilience and empathy, ultimately leading to a more balanced and fulfilling life. Artificial intelligence inclines human to reduce to users and products, due to constant usage of this technology people are dehumanized and human dignity is at toss. Only yogic disciple has the ability to fill the vacuum in modern education to mould the children into responsible emotionally and spiritually intelligence future of the country. Vivekanand envisioned that we should not be satisfied with information gathering and bread earning education but education which shapes the personality to remain balanced in any situation or turmoil of life. It echoes what Swami Vivekananda said, 'Education is the manifestation of perfection already in man.'¹⁰

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4. Conclusion

Yoga being the right art of living deals with oneself and others into the era of AI, it has lacuna where we surrender ourselves to this technology physically and mentally. Here we are digitally connected with each other but forgot to connect emotionally and empathetically. One may learn values and virtues of patience, forgiveness and the gentleness through yoga practices and not with the help of digital media. Digitalization gives us the information about how to behave but does not teach us how to imbibe these values and virtues and remain calm in conflicting situations. One who is equipped with the technology of AI does not guarantee the behaviour of peace, purity, truth, consciousness and bliss in one's daily life which can be guaranteed by yogic discipline. *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*, is an ancient Indian philosophical principle that perceives the entire world as one large, interconnected family through internet. This philosophical principle of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* aligns with the yogic principle which provides a foundation for it, which is the dire need of the today's world of conflict and stress. The era of quick solution requires developing a greater understanding of the world rather than superficial one around us and connecting more deeply with other people, regardless of their background or beliefs in virtual way than real manner. Thus, in today's complex world of emotional quotient is not sufficient rather one requires spiritual quotient i.e. spiritual quotient, then only one can manage efficiently the difficult situation. In contemporary world man is expected to respond to the situations rather than reaction as well as expected to adapt smoothly to the change of roles. Integration of emotional and spiritual intelligence with technology can facilitate the development of AI applications and systems that prioritise human values, ethics, and empathy. By infusing technology with the virtues and values of compassion, connection, and holistic growth, we can ensure the harmonious coexistence of humans and machines and bring into view a more sustainable future. Thus, yoga can bring an inclusive culture, based on the vision of oneness is the best possible means to inculcate spiritual quotient or spiritual intelligence for universal welfare and goodwill towards all living beings.

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